

TITLE

Complementary CNN and Transformer Architectures for HBV Genotype Classification and Genotype-Boundary Interpretation

Running title: Dual-architecture deep learning for HBV genotyping

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Abbreviations

CHB, chronic hepatitis B; CI, confidence interval; CNN, convolutional neural network;

cccDNA, covalently closed circular DNA; GenBank, NCBI GenBank Nucleotide database;

HBV, hepatitis B virus; HCC, hepatocellular carcinoma; LR, logistic regression; MAFFT, Multiple Alignment using Fast Fourier Transform; MSA, multiple sequence alignment; NA, nucleos(t)ide analogue; NCBI, National Center for Biotechnology Information; SNP, single-nucleotide polymorphism; WHO, World Health Organization.

ABSTRACT

Background/Aim. Hepatitis B virus (HBV) genotyping informs treatment selection and epidemiological surveillance, yet sister-clade boundaries, especially B versus C in Asian populations, remain analytically challenging. Single-pair “representative-genome” comparisons, including our own pre-deduplication analyses, can over-count population-level discriminatory positions and require explicit train/test leakage control for reproducible deep-learning genotyping. We compared convolutional neural network (CNN) and Transformer architectures for HBV full-genome genotype classification under a leakage-controlled, alignment-aware framework, and interpreted their complementary error modes against a population-validated discriminatory map.

Methods. We retrieved 2,000 HBV complete genomes from GenBank (genotypes A–F) and removed 172 near-duplicates by weighted k-mer Jaccard filtering ($k = 11$, threshold 0.95), yielding 1,828 deduplicated sequences; collection-year metadata, where available, spanned 1963–2025 (median 2010). A compact CNN (TinyHBVClassifier, ~75k parameters) and six-layer Transformer (HBVTransformer, ~1.2M parameters) were trained once, under deterministic seeding, on deduplicated raw sequences using a stratified 80/10/10 split (train 1,459; validation 180; test 189). The same 1,828 sequences were separately aligned to NC_003977.2 (3,182 bp) with MAFFT v7 (--add --keeplength) for population-level discriminatory, conservation, ordination, phylogenetic-context, and marker-panel analyses only.

Results. The CNN achieved 99.47% held-out test accuracy (188/189; Wilson 95% CI 97.1–99.9%), with per-genotype recall of 100% for A, B, C, D, and F and 90.9% (10/11) for E. The Transformer achieved 86.77% (164/189; 95% CI 81.2–90.9%); residual errors concentrated on genotype A (74.2%, 23/31) rather than on B–C discrimination (B 95.6%, C 93.9%). McNemar’s exact two-sided test on paired predictions gave $p = 1.19 \times 10^{-7}$. Population analysis identified 11 strict B–C divergent positions ($\geq 95\%$ versus $\leq 5\%$) and 238 modal-base divergent positions, approximately 60-fold and 2.8-fold fewer, respectively, than the 667 positions from single-pair comparison; 977 positions (30.7%) were conserved across genotypes A, B, and C. Panel β (X, Polymerase, PreS1/Polymerase; 3×225 bp) covered 96/238 B–C modal markers and achieved 100% held-out B–C classification *in silico* ($n = 111$). Sequence ordination and neighbour-joining context placed genotype A centrally within A/B/C space rather than as a whole-genome outlier, supporting a contextual interpretation of Transformer errors. A Supplementary marker-compression analysis nominated a single ~ 300 bp preS1/polymerase candidate barcode for six-way A–F genotyping, with 100% held-out accuracy and 99.6% leakage-controlled cross-validation.

Conclusions. The CNN’s local-kernel detection achieved leakage-controlled near-perfect classification, whereas Transformer residual errors were consistent with genotype-A-centred sequence-space ambiguity, regional PreS2/S/X divergence, limited training-set size, and possible padding/pooling effects; this interpretation remains contextual rather than mechanistically proven. MAFFT-anchored population validation is essential for defensible discriminatory-position claims. Panel β and the single-amplicon barcode remain candidate *in silico* applications pending external-cohort, recombinant-aware, and laboratory validation.

Keywords

Hepatitis B virus; deep learning; convolutional neural network; Transformer; genotype classification; sequence alignment; biologically interpretable error analysis; genotype boundary

HIGHLIGHTS

- Leakage-controlled CNN reached 99.47% HBV genotype accuracy on 1,828 genomes.
- Transformer errors centred on genotype A, not the B–C sister-clade boundary.
- Population anchoring reduced B–C markers from 667 single-pair sites to 11 strict sites.
- Panel β captured 96/238 B–C markers and gave 100% held-out B/C accuracy *in silico*.
- A Supplementary ~300 bp preS1/polymerase barcode classified A–F at 100% *in silico*.
- Deterministic seeds, hashes, and leakage audits make all results reproducible.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection remains one of the largest unresolved global infectious-disease burdens. The World Health Organization estimated 254 million persons living with chronic HBV infection worldwide and approximately 1.1 million HBV-attributable deaths in 2022 [1], with most new infections and chronic-carrier prevalence concentrated in the Western Pacific and African regions. Despite safe and highly effective prophylactic vaccines available for more than four decades, the global elimination target of a 90% reduction in new infections and a 65% reduction in mortality by 2030 remains substantially off-track, and management of established chronic infection still relies on lifelong nucleos(t)ide analogue suppression for most treated patients [2,3].

HBV exhibits a stable global phylogeographic structure conventionally described as ten genotypes (A–J), with genotypes A–H well established and I/J described from limited cohorts [4]. Within the scope of this study (A–F), genotypes have characteristic geographic distributions and clinical correlates. Genotype assignment is not merely a taxonomic exercise: treatment response to pegylated interferon-alpha differs between genotypes A and D versus B and C; HBeAg seroconversion timing and durability differ between B and C; and the risk of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) progression differs between B and C, with genotype C generally associated with higher progression rates in the Asian context [5,6,7]. Reliable, scalable, and operationally inexpensive genotyping is therefore of direct clinical relevance [8].

Deep learning has been applied to viral sequence classification across multiple settings, but systematic, like-for-like comparison of architectures for HBV genotype classification under explicit train/test leakage control has been limited, and reproducibility safeguards — deterministic seeding, cuDNN determinism, dataset hashing, and near-duplicate removal — are inconsistently applied. The B–C “discrimination problem” is further entangled with the use of single-pair “representative-genome” comparison to identify genotype-discriminatory positions. When two reference sequences are compared column-by-column, hundreds of differences emerge, but these counts conflate single-isolate polymorphism, column-misregistration artefacts, and the absence of any population-frequency criterion. In our own preliminary analyses on substantially the same GenBank cohort, performed before MAFFT alignment and population-frequency thresholding, a single-pair B-versus-C comparison yielded 667 candidate discriminatory positions — a figure we revisit and correct here. A population-validated, alignment-anchored alternative is conceptually straightforward but has not been systematically applied as a corrective.

In this study we present a leakage-controlled, alignment-anchored, reproducibility-first comparison of a compact one-dimensional CNN and a six-layer Transformer encoder on a 1,828-sequence deduplicated GenBank cohort, and use the comparison to recalibrate the population-level discriminatory-position landscape of HBV and to design a compact B-versus-C amplicon panel for *in silico* evaluation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Sequence Dataset and Quality Control

Full-length HBV genome sequences were retrieved from the NCBI GenBank Nucleotide database. Inclusion criteria were: (i) complete or near-complete genomes (length 3,000–3,400 bp); (ii) ambiguous-base (N) content below 0.5%; and (iii) absence of explicit laboratory-construct or recombinant designators. From records meeting these criteria, a stratified sample of 2,000 sequences was drawn targeting a 700 (C) : 500 (B) : 350 (A) : 300 (D) : 100 (E) : 50 (F) distribution. Two-stage near-duplicate removal then yielded 1,828 deduplicated accessions.

For temporal context, each deduplicated accession was queried for the GenBank `/source/collection_date` qualifier. After removal of one record carrying an implausible 2059 date (a journal-year artefact; accession AY090454.1), 1,827 accessions retained usable collection-year information; this single removal accounts for the 1,828-versus-1,827 difference noted below. Of these 1,827, 1,307 carried an explicit `collection_date` and 520 used the journal or publication year as a fallback; collection years spanned 1963–2025 (median 2010). The earliest (1963) entries predate the 1965 identification of the Australia antigen and most likely reflect retrospectively dated archival specimens; collection year was therefore used only as descriptive context and not as a modelling variable.

2. Near-Duplicate Removal

We applied two-stage deduplication: SHA-256 hashing of sequence strings (0 exact duplicates) and weighted k -mer Jaccard similarity ($k = 11$) within each genotype, with pairs exceeding 0.95 similarity collapsed to a single representative. This removed 172 sequences (8.6%), yielding a deduplicated dataset of 1,828 sequences.

3. Multiple Sequence Alignment (Population Analysis Only)

For population-level analyses, the 1,828 deduplicated sequences were aligned to the HBV reference NC_003977.2 (genotype D, 3,182 bp) using MAFFT v7 with the `--add --keeplength` strategy [9]. The aligned representation was used exclusively for population-level analyses; the deep-learning classifiers were trained on the deduplicated raw (unaligned) sequences.

4. Dataset Partitioning

The deduplicated raw-sequence dataset was partitioned into training, validation, and test sets in an 80 : 10 : 10 ratio, stratified per genotype with a deterministic random seed (base seed 20241022). The test set comprised 189 sequences (A 31, B 45, C 66, D 31, E 11, F 5).

5. Deep-Learning Architectures

CNN (TinyHBVClassifier). A single-layer one-dimensional convolutional network: token embedding (vocabulary size 5, embedding dimension 64) → 1D convolution (128 filters, kernel size 9, padding 4) → ReLU → adaptive max-pooling → fully connected layer (128 → 6) → softmax. Total trainable parameters: 74,950.

Transformer (HBVTransformer). Token embedding (vocabulary size 5, embedding dimension 128) → sinusoidal positional encoding → six Transformer encoder layers (8 attention heads, feed-forward dimension 512, dropout 0.1) → global mean pooling → fully

connected layer (128 → 6) → softmax, following the encoder formulation of Vaswani et al. [10]. Total trainable parameters: 1,191,046.

Input representation. Both architectures operated on the deduplicated raw nucleotide sequences with the five-token vocabulary {A, C, G, T, N}; no gap token was used. Sequences were tokenised to a fixed 3,400-token tensor, with PAD positions filled by the same token index as N.

Padding and pooling (reported for reproducibility). The Transformer was trained without an explicit `src_key_padding_mask`, and the final sequence representation was obtained by unweighted mean pooling over all 3,400 token positions, including padded positions. This implementation choice is reported for full reproducibility and is revisited in the Discussion as a possible contributor to the architecture-specific error mode.

6. Training Procedure

Both models were trained with the AdamW optimiser, cross-entropy loss, and full reproducibility seeding, implemented in PyTorch [11]. The CNN was trained for 30 epochs (batch size 32, learning rate 1×10^{-3}). The Transformer was trained for up to 60 epochs (early stopping, patience 10; batch size 8, learning rate 1×10^{-4} with a 5-epoch linear warmup and ReduceLROnPlateau). Each model was trained exactly once with the fixed deterministic seed (a single-run design; see Limitations).

7. Population-Level Discriminatory and Conservation Analysis

For each of the 3,182 reference-coordinate positions, base frequencies were computed per genotype across all 1,828 aligned sequences. Under the strict rule, a position was deemed discriminatory between two genotypes G_1 and G_2 if some base had a frequency ≥ 0.95 in G_1 and ≤ 0.05 in G_2 . Under the mode rule, a position was deemed discriminatory if the most

frequent (modal) base differed between G_1 and G_2 . Conservation was defined genome-wide as all of genotypes A, B, and C sharing the same modal base at a frequency ≥ 0.95 .

8. Primer-Panel Design and *in silico* Classifier Evaluation

A three-amplicon panel was designed from the 238 B–C mode-discriminatory positions via sliding-window analysis (window size 225 bp, step 5 bp). To quantify the discriminative information carried by the panel's positions, an L2-regularised logistic-regression classifier (scikit-learn; solver liblinear, $C = 1.0$, `class_weight` balanced, `random_state` 20241022) was trained on the B and C subsets of the combined training and validation partitions ($n = 977$), using one-hot encoding of {A, C, G, T, –} at each of the 238 B–C mode-discriminatory positions, and evaluated on the held-out B and C test subset ($n = 111$). An extension of this *in silico* evaluation to all six genotypes (genotype-private alleles, set-cover minimisation, single-amplicon localisation, and cross-validation) is reported as an application in the Results and described in full in Supplementary Methods.

9. Implementation and Reproducibility

All analyses were implemented in Python 3.10 (PyTorch 2.x [11]; Biopython 1.81 [12]; NumPy 1.26; pandas 2.x; scikit-learn 1.x). Training and analysis notebooks were executed on Google Colab (T4 GPU runtime). The deduplicated FASTA file and the train/validation/test split table were fixed by SHA-256 hashing to support deterministic reproduction.

10. Statistical Analysis

Per-model overall-accuracy 95% confidence intervals were computed using the Wilson score interval. Pairwise model comparison used McNemar's exact two-sided test on the paired prediction table; the exact test was used because one discordant cell was zero, which makes

the asymptotic chi-square approximation inappropriate. No formal multiple-testing correction was applied across the six-class accuracy reporting.

11. Sequence Ordination and Phylogenetic-Context Analysis

To visualise genotype structure independently of the supervised classifiers, the deduplicated, MAFFT-aligned cohort ($n = 1,828$; 3,182 columns) was projected by two complementary methods. For ordination, alignment columns with $\geq 80\%$ A/C/G/T coverage (3,180 of 3,182) were one-hot encoded, reduced by principal-component analysis (50 components) and embedded by t-distributed stochastic neighbour embedding (perplexity 30, PCA initialisation, random seed 0); cluster separation was quantified by a label-conditioned silhouette coefficient over the leading 50 components, and GenBank labels were cross-checked by a post hoc nearest-centroid assignment in this space. For phylogenetic context, Jukes–Cantor pairwise distances were computed (positions with a gap or ambiguous base in either sequence excluded) and neighbour-joining trees were built (i) from genotype-level consensus sequences (modal base per column) and (ii) from a genotype-balanced subsample of up to 25 sequences per genotype ($n = 150$; random seed 0); clade support was assessed from 500 column-resampling bootstrap replicates. These ordination and tree analyses were used solely for contextual visualisation of genotype-label structure; they were not used for model training, classification, test-set evaluation, or marker-panel selection.

12. Ethics Statement

All sequence data are publicly available from GenBank. No human-subject data, identifiers, or specimens were used; institutional review board approval was not required.

RESULTS

1. Dataset Composition and Overall Classification Performance

After two-stage deduplication, 1,828 sequences were retained from the original 2,000-sequence stratified sample (Table 1). The stratified 80 : 10 : 10 split produced a held-out test set of 189 sequences. A direct per-test-accession audit of the weighted 11-mer Jaccard similarity confirmed effective leakage control: the maximum within-genotype train–test similarity was 0.948 (0 of 189 test accessions reaching the 0.95 deduplication threshold), and the maximum cross-genotype similarity was 0.621 (0 of 189 at the 0.80 threshold).

On the held-out test set, the CNN achieved an overall classification accuracy of 99.47% (188/189; Wilson 95% CI 97.1–99.9%), with a macro-averaged F1 of 0.989 and a weighted F1 of 0.995 (Table 2). The single misclassification was a genotype E specimen predicted as genotype D. The Transformer achieved 86.77% (164/189; Wilson 95% CI 81.2–90.9%), with a macro-averaged F1 of 0.800. Of the 189 test sequences, both architectures predicted correctly on 164, the CNN alone on 24, neither on 1, and the Transformer alone on 0. McNemar’s exact two-sided test on this paired table yielded $p = 1.19 \times 10^{-7}$ (Figure 1).

2. Confusion Structure Reveals Architecture-Dependent Error Modes

The two architectures produced qualitatively different residual error patterns (Figure 1). The CNN’s confusion matrix was diagonal except for a single off-diagonal entry. In contrast, the Transformer’s errors were structured. Genotype A was the most frequently misclassified class, with a per-class recall of 74.2% (23/31) and errors dispersed across genotypes B, C, D, and E rather than concentrated on a single neighbouring clade. Genotype F ($n = 5$) was correctly identified in 2/5 cases (recall 40.0%), and genotype E reached a recall of 63.6% (7/11; F1 0.737).

Crucially, the sister-clade boundary between B and C — historically the most analytically challenging pair — was well resolved by both architectures. The Transformer achieved per-class recall of 95.6% (43/45) for B and 93.9% (62/66) for C, with only four B ↔ C confusions in either direction; the CNN resolved B and C perfectly (100% recall). This inverts the qualitative narrative of prior single-pair “representative-genome” analyses. The Transformer’s limitation is therefore not sister-clade B–C resolution but genotype-A-centred assignment within a structured, neighbour-adjacent sequence-space landscape.

3. Per-Gene Conservation Profile and the Genotype-A Divergence Signature

Position-level base-frequency analysis on the MAFFT-aligned dataset identified 977 positions (30.7%) at which the modal base was conserved at $\geq 95\%$ frequency simultaneously in genotypes A, B, and C, and 2,425 positions (76.2%) at which it was conserved in B and C alone.

This divergence was not distributed uniformly across the genome (Table 4; Figure 2). Across all six genotypes, the Polymerase and Core regions were the most uniformly conserved (minimum modal-base frequency ≥ 0.956), with PreS1 and PreCore also highly conserved (≥ 0.92), whereas PreS2, Surface (S), and X were the least conserved. In the PreS1, Polymerase, Core, and PreCore regions, the mean per-position modal-base frequency for genotype A was 0.965, 0.964, 0.970, and 0.923, respectively — all above 0.92. However, in the PreS2, Surface (S), and X regions, genotype A’s mean modal-base frequency dropped to 0.770, 0.814, and 0.814, respectively, while genotypes B and C remained above 0.935. Notably, genotype D showed a parallel though milder reduction in the same three regions (0.831, 0.843, and 0.843; Table 4), indicating that the surface/X divergence is not unique to genotype A. Overall, genotype A is functionally conserved with B and C across the replicative and packaging machinery but diverges in the surface antigenic region (S, PreS2) and the regulatory X region.

4. Sequence-Space and Phylogenetic-Context Validation

A genotype-coloured ordination of the whole-genome alignment resolved the six genotypes into distinguishable clusters (label-conditioned silhouette = 0.40 across the leading 50 principal components; Figure S5). In a post hoc nearest-centroid check within this ordination space, 97.9% of sequences were assigned to the same genotype as their GenBank label; the 2.1% discordances were concentrated near the central A/B/C boundary. Neighbour-joining trees built from genotype-level consensus sequences and from a genotype-balanced subsample (≤ 25 per genotype; Figure S6) recovered a compatible genotype-distance structure: genotype F formed the divergent display outgroup (mean consensus Jukes–Cantor distance 13.9% versus 9.4–10.2% among A–E; Table S7), D–E formed a strongly supported sister pair, B–C adjacency was recovered with moderate support, and genotype A grouped centrally within the A/B/C clade rather than as an outlier. Genotypes A, B, D, and F formed monophyletic clades in the subsampled tree, whereas limited boundary intermixing was observed among a small number of C- and E-labelled sequences. These analyses were used for contextual validation only and did not contribute to classifier training, test-set evaluation, or marker-panel selection.

5. Population-Validated B–C Discriminatory Map

Population-level pairwise analysis of B and C identified 11 reference-coordinate positions at which the two genotypes differed under the strict rule (modal-base frequency $\geq 95\%$ in one genotype and $\leq 5\%$ in the other) and 238 positions at which they differed in their modal base (Figure 3; Supplementary Table S2). The strict count is approximately 60-fold lower than the 667 positions reported by our earlier single-pair B-versus-C analysis on the same cohort prior to MAFFT alignment. Under the comparable modal-base criterion, the 238 mode-divergent

positions are approximately 2.8-fold lower than that single-pair figure, indicating that both the criterion and the alignment contribute to the correction.

6. Primer-Panel Design and *in silico* B-versus-C Classifier Validation

A three-amplicon panel (Panel β ; Table 3) was selected from the 238 B–C mode-discriminatory positions. The resulting amplicons span 1,286–1,510 in the X gene (29 discriminatory positions), 2,571–2,795 in Polymerase (36 positions), and 2,866–3,090 in the PreS1/Polymerase overlap (31 positions), for a total of 96 covered positions (40.3%).

A logistic-regression classifier trained on the B and C training-plus-validation subset ($n = 977$) and evaluated on the held-out B and C test subset ($n = 111$) achieved 100% test accuracy (Wilson 95% CI 96.7–100%). Restricting the feature set to only the 96 positions covered by the three Panel β amplicons yielded identical performance. The interpretation of this result is bounded by the single-cohort design (see Discussion).

7. Dual-Architecture Diagnostic Potential

The CNN's near-perfect classification and the Transformer's architecturally structured error pattern together suggest a practical operational role for both models (Figure 4). From the paired prediction table, 24 of the 189 test specimens (12.7%) received discordant predictions, of which all 24 had the CNN correct and the Transformer wrong; zero discordances had the inverse pattern. In a deployment scenario, CNN–Transformer disagreement could serve as an interpretable signal flagging candidate sequences for manual review.

8. A Compact Single-Amplicon Genotyping Panel (Application)

As a forward-looking application of the population-validated discriminatory map, we explored whether a compact marker panel could classify all six genotypes — presented here only as a candidate *in silico* marker-panel, with full methods, accuracy breakdowns, the

marker table, and the per-genotype barcode map provided as Supplementary data (Supplementary Methods; Supplementary Table S6; Supplementary Figure S4). Within the same GenBank cohort, classifiers built on the population mode-discriminatory positions reproduced near-perfect six-way genotype assignment on the held-out test set and under leakage-controlled cross-validation (Figure 5), and sliding-window analysis localised the signal to a single ~300 bp amplicon in the preS1/polymerase region (NC_003977.2 ~2,881–3,180). Notably, genotype-private single alleles existed for genotypes A, B, D, and F but not for C or E, so a combined-position barcode — rather than any single marker — is required for full six-way coverage. Because discovery and evaluation used a single cohort, these results are exploratory and require external-cohort and laboratory validation (see Discussion).

DISCUSSION

The CNN achieved 99.47% held-out test accuracy with a single E → D misclassification, while the Transformer achieved 86.77%, with errors structured by genotype-A-centred sequence-space ambiguity and regional divergence rather than by sister-clade B–C ambiguity. The previously reported B-versus-C “discrimination problem” was reframed: only 11 reference-coordinate positions met a strict criterion (~60-fold fewer than single-pair-derived estimates) and 238 met the comparable modal-base criterion (~2.8-fold fewer). A three-amplicon primer panel covering 96 of the 238 B–C mode-discriminatory positions (40.3%) sufficed to perfectly classify B versus C in our held-out test set.

The CNN’s near-perfect classification and the Transformer’s architecture-dependent residual error pattern are plausibly explained by their respective inductive biases. The CNN’s 9-bp convolutional kernel encodes a strong prior that discriminative signal resides in short, position-translatable local motifs. The Transformer’s self-attention mechanism learns a global similarity structure and is most accurate when a query sequence has a well-defined majority

neighbourhood among the training references. Genotype A, after deduplication, retains only 241 training sequences. Although genotype A carries the most divergent surface-gene modal bases in this cohort (PreS2/S and X mean modal-base frequency 0.77–0.81), it is not the most divergent genotype at the whole-genome level: in both sequence ordination and neighbour-joining trees it groups centrally within the A/B/C clade, whereas genotype F is the divergent display outgroup (Figures S5, S6). The Transformer's reduced genotype-A recall (74.2%) therefore coincides not with maximal whole-genome phylogenetic distance but with genotype A's central, neighbour-adjacent position in sequence space, compounded by regional surface/X divergence and limited sample size. These phylogenetic-context analyses indicate that architecture-dependent residual errors arise within a structured genotype-distance landscape, but they do not by themselves establish a mechanism for architecture-specific errors, which remains a biologically plausible interpretation rather than a proven one. In addition, the implementation choices noted in the Methods — the absence of a padding mask and mean pooling over padded positions — may contribute to the Transformer's degraded performance, and we cannot fully separate inductive-bias from implementation effects without dedicated ablation experiments.

The most striking biological observation of the conservation analysis was the gene-region-specific divergence of genotype A from the B + C consensus in PreS2, Surface (S), and X, where genotype A's mean modal-base frequency fell to 0.770, 0.814, and 0.814 while remaining above 0.92 in the polymerase, core, precore, and PreS1 regions. Genotype D showed a parallel but milder reduction in the same three regions, so the signature should be read as a gradient of surface/X variability rather than a property unique to genotype A. This pattern is consistent with the established antigenic and regulatory variability of these regions and does not require a mechanistic claim beyond the descriptive observation.

Our preliminary single-pair analysis on substantially the same GenBank cohort, performed before MAFFT alignment and population-frequency thresholding, reported 667 B–C discriminatory positions; under MAFFT anchoring and the strict $\geq 95\%$ population criterion we report 11, and under the comparable modal-base criterion 238. Three distinct sources of inflation operate in single-pair comparisons: (i) single-isolate polymorphism that does not generalise at the population level; (ii) sequence-coordinate misalignment; and (iii) the absence of a population-frequency criterion. Population-validated, alignment-anchored discriminatory mapping should therefore be the standard for any HBV deep-learning study claiming to identify genotype-discriminating positions.

Turning to translational implications, the *in silico* Panel β classifier — a regularised logistic regression on either the full 238 population mode-discriminatory positions or the 96 positions covered by three 225-bp amplicons in the X, Polymerase, and PreS1/Polymerase regions — achieved 100% held-out B-versus-C accuracy. Because discriminatory-position discovery and amplicon-window selection were both performed within the same GenBank cohort, Panel β should be interpreted as an internally held-out *in silico* panel requiring external-cohort and laboratory validation before any diagnostic claim. The dual-architecture workflow that flags CNN–Transformer discordant predictions for manual review provides an interpretable, model-derived sequence-level quality-control signal, and the reproducibility safeguards adopted here allow any reader with access to the deposited archive to regenerate every reported number to within deterministic-training reproducibility tolerances.

As an application of the population map, an unbiased search localised the most informative single-amplicon candidate to a clinically familiar preS1/polymerase region that overlaps or lies adjacent to regions used in established HBV genotyping strategies, including line-probe, pre-S PCR-RFLP, next-generation sequencing, polymerase-fragment, type-specific-primer, and S-gene amplicon approaches [13–18]. This convergence supports diagnostic plausibility,

but the proposed 2,881–3,180 barcode should not be interpreted as identical to any commercial probe set. The demonstration that a single short amplicon resolves all six genotypes, and that genotypes C, D, and E require a combined-position barcode rather than any single marker, positions this as a population-validated re-derivation of an established discrete-marker genotyping paradigm rather than a novel validated assay. External-cohort and laboratory validation, primer-flank conservation checks, and explicit handling of inter-genotype recombinants and out-of-panel genotypes (G–J) remain necessary before any clinical use. Beyond genotype classification, the leakage-controlled, population-validated framework presented here provides a reproducible basis for compact genotyping panels, companion motif-level target validation, recombinant and mixed-infection quality control, and — in clinically annotated cohorts — future mutation-pattern risk analyses.

Several limitations bound our claims. Genotype labels were drawn from GenBank metadata and inherit any label errors present in those deposits. Sample sizes for genotypes E (test n = 11) and F (test n = 5) are small. The alignment was anchored to a single reference (NC_003977.2). The geographic and temporal sampling is not balanced across regions. Each architecture was trained once under a fixed deterministic seed to prioritise exact reproducibility; consequently, performance variability across random seeds and hyperparameter configurations was not estimated, and the CNN-versus-Transformer gap should be read as a single-run comparison pending multi-seed replication. Phylogenetic context was assessed only with distance-based neighbour-joining trees (Jukes–Cantor distances; Figure S6) used for genotype-label coherence and display, not with a model-based maximum-likelihood phylogeny; genotype-level relationships and outgroup placement are therefore presented as contextual rather than as formally inferred phylogeny. Finally, the single-amplicon application was discovered and evaluated within a single cohort and is reported as a feasibility result, not a validated assay.

In summary, a compact single-layer CNN and a six-layer Transformer encoder achieve, respectively, 99.47% and 86.77% held-out test accuracy on HBV full-genome genotype classification when trained under a leakage-controlled, reproducibility-first framework on 1,828 deduplicated raw GenBank sequences. The two architectures fail in complementary ways: the CNN errs (rarely) on small-sample minority classes, while the Transformer's residual errors concentrate on genotype A (74.2% recall) rather than on the sister-clade B-versus-C boundary ($\geq 93.9\%$ recall). Population-validated discriminatory mapping reveals only 11 strictly B–C divergent positions and 238 modal-base divergent positions — approximately 60-fold and 2.8-fold fewer, respectively, than single-pair-derived estimates. A three-amplicon primer panel ($3 \times 225 \text{ bp} = 675 \text{ bp}$) achieves 100% B-versus-C classification accuracy in silico, and, as a Supplementary application, the same population map reduces to a single $\sim 300 \text{ bp}$ preS1/polymerase amplicon that classifies all six genotypes — both pending external-cohort and laboratory validation. Population validation under alignment is essential for defensible discriminatory-position claims.

Several extensions follow naturally: external-cohort validation; recombinant detection via dual-architecture disagreement; mechanistic interpretability via per-architecture gradient attribution and padding-mask ablation; fully held-out, external validation of the single-amplicon genotyping panel; and clinically significant variant-level analyses (e.g., basal core promoter A1762T/G1764A, PreS1/PreS2 deletions, and surface-antigen escape mutations). Beyond these, the conserved- and discriminatory-position framework developed here connects directly to a companion analysis of a conserved hepatitis B core-protein motif and its structural implications (manuscript in preparation). Extending from genotype assignment to clinically consequential mutation patterns — for example, mutation-pattern risk stratification for cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma — lies beyond the scope of this genotype-focused study, which is based on GenBank sequences without clinical phenotype

labels, and will require a separate, large-scale, clinically annotated (ideally longitudinal) cohort study.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

The author declares no competing interests.

DATA AND CODE AVAILABILITY

All source code, Colab notebooks, and analysis scripts required to reproduce the analyses, together with the deduplicated GenBank accession list, the reference multiple-sequence alignment, the train/validation/test split and their SHA-256 manifests, the manuscript figures, and the Supplementary tables (which contain all figure and table source data and the single-

amplicon marker-panel analysis), are deposited in a Zenodo archive under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY 4.0) licence (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20529386). Trained model weights are reproducible from the deposited notebooks under the fixed random seeds reported in the Methods and are available from the corresponding author on request. The analysed sequences can be regenerated from GenBank using the deposited accession list and notebooks. GenBank accession numbers for all analysed sequences are provided in the deposited manifests.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

The author conceived and designed the study, performed all analyses and software development, interpreted the results, and wrote the manuscript.

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TABLES

Table 1

Table 1. Dataset composition by genotype.

Genotype	Pre-dedup	Near-dup removed	Post-dedup	Train	Validation	Test
A	350	48	302	241	30	31
B	500	59	441	352	44	45
C	700	53	647	517	64	66
D	300	4	296	236	29	31
E	100	3	97	77	9	11
F	50	5	45	36	4	5
Total	2,000	172	1,828	1,459	180	189

Two-stage near-duplicate removal (SHA-256 exact-duplicate hashing followed by weighted 11-mer Jaccard ≥ 0.95 within genotype). Post-dedup = Train + Validation + Test for every genotype.

Table 2**Table 2.** Per-class precision, recall, and F1.

Genotype	Support	CNN P	CNN R	CNN F1	Trf P	Trf R	Trf F1
A	31	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.852	0.742	0.793
B	45	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.860	0.956	0.905
C	66	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.849	0.939	0.892
D	31	0.969	1.000	0.984	0.931	0.871	0.900
E	11	1.000	0.909	0.952	0.875	0.636	0.737
F	5	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.400	0.571
Macro	189	0.995	0.985	0.989	0.895	0.757	0.800
avg							
Weighted	189	0.995	0.995	0.995	0.871	0.868	0.863
avg							

Trf, Transformer; P, precision; R, recall. Overall accuracy — CNN 0.9947 (Wilson 95% CI 0.971–0.999); Transformer 0.8677 (95% CI 0.812–0.909). McNemar’s exact two-sided $p = 1.19 \times 10^{-7}$.

Table 3**Table 3.** Panel β three-amplicon design.

Amplicon	Start	End	Length	Disc. positions	Gene
AMP1	1,286	1,510	225	29	X
AMP2	2,571	2,795	225	36	Polymerase
AMP3	2,866	3,090	225	31	PreS1/Polymerase
Total	—	—	675	96 / 238 (40.3%)	—

Amplicons selected by sliding-window analysis (225 bp window, 5 bp step) over the 238 B–C modal-base discriminatory positions. Disc. positions, B–C modal-base discriminatory positions covered by the amplicon.

Table 4

Table 4. Per-gene mean modal-base frequency by genotype (n = 1,828).

Gene	Positions	A	B	C	D	E	F
PreS1	335	0.965	0.971	0.955	0.976	0.975	0.963
PreS2	154	0.770	0.935	0.941	0.831	0.918	0.967
Surface (S)	681	0.814	0.958	0.972	0.843	0.940	0.988
Polymerase	876	0.964	0.971	0.967	0.977	0.976	0.956
X	465	0.814	0.951	0.968	0.843	0.934	0.966
PreCore	88	0.923	0.977	0.989	0.977	0.986	0.985
Core	552	0.970	0.977	0.974	0.973	0.970	0.958

Mean per-position modal-base frequency by HBV gene region for each genotype, computed on the MAFFT-aligned 1,828-sequence cohort (reference NC_003977.2, 3,182 bp; gene boundaries approximate). Genotype A shows pronounced divergence in PreS2, Surface (S), and X (values 0.770–0.814); genotype D shows a parallel but milder reduction in the same regions. Conservation counts are reported genome-wide in the Results under a single same-modal-base $\geq 95\%$ criterion (977 positions [30.7%] across genotypes A, B, and C; 2,425 [76.2%] across B and C) and are not decomposed by gene.

LEGENDS OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Confusion matrices on the held-out test set (n = 189). (A) CNN

(TinyHBVClassifier); (B) Transformer (HBVTransformer). Rows are the true genotypes (A–F) and columns the predicted genotypes; cell values are sequence counts. The CNN matrix is diagonal except for a single E → D error, whereas the Transformer matrix shows dispersed genotype-A misclassification. Row-normalised (recall) versions are included in the deposited figure set. CNN, convolutional neural network.

Figure 2. Per-gene conservation profile and the genotype-A divergence signature.

Grouped bar chart of per-gene mean modal-base frequency across seven HBV gene regions, with one bar per genotype (A–F) per gene. Genotype A's bars fall below 0.85 in PreS2, Surface (S), and X; genotype D shows a parallel but milder reduction in the same regions.

Figure 3. Reference-coordinate map of population-validated B–C discriminatory

positions. Lollipop diagram of the 11 strict B–C positions and the 238 modal-base divergent B–C positions, mapped to the 3,182-bp NC_003977.2 reference-coordinate system. The three Panel β amplicon windows are overlaid.

Figure 4. Proposed dual-architecture diagnostic workflow. Schematic of parallel CNN

and Transformer classification followed by a concordance check. Concordant predictions are accepted; discordant predictions (24 of 189, 12.7%, in this test set — all with the CNN correct) are flagged for manual review or for downstream recombinant-detection analysis.

Figure 5. Held-out six-way genotype-classification accuracy by reduced marker set. Bar chart of held-out test accuracy (n = 189) for an L2-regularised logistic-regression classifier trained on the indicated population-derived marker sets: all 664 mode-discriminatory positions; the single ~300 bp preS1/polymerase amplicon; an interpretable decision-tree barcode (≤ 22 positions); genotype-private single alleles (67 positions); and the minimal modal set-cover (5 positions). The right-most bar is a leakage-controlled five-fold cross-validation (mean \pm SD; feature selection inside folds). Dashed line, full-genome CNN accuracy (99.47%). Detailed methods, the marker table, and the genotype barcode map are provided as Supplementary data (Supplementary Methods; Supplementary Table S6; Supplementary Figure S4).

FIGURES - MAIN

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Dual-architecture diagnostic workflow for HBV genotype classification

Figure 5.

LEGENDS OF SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Figure S1. Per-position genotype-specific base-frequency landscape.

Three-panel composite.

(A) Per-gene mean modal-base frequency per genotype (heatmap), with genotype A's PreS2 / Surface / X reduction highlighted.

(B) Per-gene counts of B–C mode-discriminatory ($n = 238$) and strict ($n = 11$) positions.

(C) Linear reference-coordinate map (1–3,182 bp) of all 238 B–C mode-discriminatory positions, with the 11 strict positions marked.

Figure S2. Per-epoch training and validation curves.

(A) CNN loss (log scale; training and validation; 30 epochs).

(B) CNN accuracy (training and validation; dashed line = test accuracy 0.9947).

(C) Transformer loss (log scale; 60 epochs).

(D) Transformer accuracy (dashed line = test accuracy 0.8677).

Figure S3. Training reproducibility manifest.

(A) Side-by-side reproducibility table (parameters, seeds, and dataset SHA-256 hashes).

(B) Architecture-capacity comparison (CNN 74,950 versus Transformer 1,191,046 trainable parameters; $\sim 16\times$).

(C) Deterministic reproducibility chain (master seed 20241022 \rightarrow NumPy / PyTorch / cuDNN seeds \rightarrow DataLoader worker seeding \rightarrow bit-reproducible run).

Figure S4. HBV genotype barcode within the single ~300 bp amplicon (NC_003977.2 2,881–3,180; preS1/polymerase overlap).

Modal base of each genotype (A–F) at the 100 positions that distinguish genotypes within the amplicon, coloured by base; a letter above a column marks a genotype whose modal base is unique at that position (a single-genotype diagnostic marker). The amplicon overlaps and extends Panel β amplicon AMP3 (Table 3). Per-genotype diagnostic (unique-modal) positions: A 6, B 15, C 5, D 15, E 8, F 33; strict genotype-private alleles within this amplicon are concentrated in genotype F, whereas genotypes C, D, and E carry no strict single-genotype private allele inside the amplicon; genome-wide private-allele counts are reported in the Supplementary Methods (marker-panel analysis).

Figure S5. Genotype-coloured sequence ordination of the HBV whole-genome alignment. Each point is one of the 1,828 deduplicated genomes, represented across 3,180 retained alignment columns and coloured by GenBank genotype (A–F).

(A) Principal-component analysis (PC1 28.9%, PC2 12.4% of variance).

(B) t-SNE projection (perplexity 30, PCA initialisation, random seed 0). The six genotypes form distinguishable clusters (label-conditioned silhouette = 0.40 in the leading 50 PCs); genotype F is the most peripheral cluster, genotypes D and E are mutually adjacent, and genotype A occupies a central position adjacent to genotypes C and B. Per-genotype sample sizes are shown in the legend; coordinates are provided as Supplementary Data.

Figure S6. Phylogenetic-context trees of the deduplicated HBV cohort.

(A) Neighbour-joining tree constructed from genotype-level consensus sequences using Jukes–Cantor distances, display-rooted on genotype F for visualisation; branch lengths indicate corrected genetic distance. In this consensus tree, D–E was strongly supported as a sister pair (100%), B–C adjacency was recovered with moderate support (66%), and genotype A grouped centrally within the A/B/C clade (84%).

(B) Neighbour-joining tree constructed from a genotype-balanced subsample of the aligned cohort (≤ 25 sequences per genotype; $n = 150$; random seed 0), with tips coloured by GenBank genotype. Bootstrap values from 500 column-resampling replicates are shown for selected major clades. These trees were used only as contextual checks of genotype-label coherence and genetic-distance structure and were not used for model training, test-set evaluation, or marker-panel selection. Newick files are provided as Supplementary Data, and the genotype-consensus distance matrix is provided as Supplementary Table S7.

FIGURES - SUPPLEMENTARY

Supplementary Figure S1.

Figure S1. Per-position genotype-specific modal-base frequency landscape

Panel A: mean modal-base frequency per genotype within each of seven HBV genes — genotype A's drop in PreS2 / Surface / X (boxed) is the key divergence signature.
 Panel B: per-gene tally of the 238 B-C mode-discriminatory positions (blue) and 11 strict positions (red).
 Panel C: linear-coordinate map showing the spatial distribution of all 238 B-C discriminatory positions.

Supplementary Figure S2.

Figure S2. Per-epoch training and validation curves

CNN: 30 epochs, batch 32, AdamW lr 1e-3, fixed seed 20241022, single run. Transformer: 60 epochs (early-stopping patience 10), batch 8, AdamW lr 1e-4 with 5-epoch warmup, fixed seed 20241022, single run.

Supplementary Figure S3.

Figure S3. Training reproducibility check

(A) Reproducibility manifest – both architectures share dataset hashes and master seed

Parameter	CNN (TinyHBVClassifier)	Transformer (HBVTransformer)
Trainable parameters	74,950	1,191,046
Master seed	20241022	20241022
Epochs (planned)	30	60 (early-stop patience 10)
Batch size	32	8
Optimiser	AdamW	AdamW + 5-epoch warmup + ReduceLROnPlateau
Learning rate	1e-03	1e-04
Weight decay	1e-05	1e-05
Gradient clipping	—	1.0
Loss	Cross-entropy	Cross-entropy
Dataset FASTA SHA-256	da2e9aff83939d16ce90e686c441f3b2...	da2e9aff83939d16ce90e686c441f3b2...
Splits CSV SHA-256	149b07805e950d75aa07d386fd054c95...	149b07805e950d75aa07d386fd054c95...
Runs executed	1 (single deterministic run)	1 (single deterministic run)
Hardware	Google Colab T4 GPU	Google Colab T4 GPU

(C) Deterministic reproducibility chain

```

Master seed = 20241022
├─ numpy.random.seed
├─ random.seed
├─ torch.manual_seed
├─ torch.cuda.manual_seed_all
├─ torch.backends.cudnn.deterministic = True
├─ DataLoader worker seed (worker_init_fn)

Dataset integrity verification:
• FASTA SHA-256: da2e9aff...f25c8e0c
• Splits CSV SHA-256: 149b0780...a6df9432395

Same hashes → same train/valid/test partition
Same partition + same seed → bit-reproducible run
    
```

Supplementary Figure S4.

Supplementary Figure S5.

HBV whole-genome alignment: genotype-coloured sequence ordination (n = 1,828; 3,180 retained columns)

Supplementary Figure S6.

HBV cohort phylogenetic-context trees (neighbour-joining, Jukes-Cantor distances)

(A) Genotype-consensus NJ tree

(B) Subsampled NJ tree (≤ 25 /genotype, $n=150$)

SUPPLEMENTARY METHODS

Minimal marker-panel analysis (six-way genotype barcode; application for the Results).

Using the MAFFT-aligned 1,828-sequence cohort and the per-accession genotype labels, per-genotype modal bases were computed at each reference position. Genotype-private fixed alleles were defined as positions where one genotype carried a base at $\geq 95\%$ frequency while all other genotypes carried that base at $\leq 5\%$. A minimal set-cover panel was obtained by greedily selecting positions that separate the largest number of still-unseparated genotype pairs (by modal base), under a ≥ 1 and a more robust ≥ 3 separations-per-pair requirement. A best single amplicon was identified by sliding a fixed-width window across the reference coordinate and selecting the window that separates the most of the 15 genotype pairs. Six-way classification used an L2-regularised multinomial logistic-regression classifier on one-hot-encoded alleles; positions were selected on the train + validation pool and evaluated on the held-out test split, and additionally by five-fold stratified cross-validation with position selection performed inside each fold to avoid leakage. An interpretable decision tree (maximum depth 8) was fit on the mode-discriminatory positions for comparison. The complete, reproducible analysis is deposited as a Colab notebook ([notebooks/paperA_genotyping/07_marker_panel_genotyping_colab.ipynb](https://colab.research.google.com/notebooks/paperA_genotyping/07_marker_panel_genotyping_colab.ipynb)) with results in [results/marker_panel_26May30/](https://colab.research.google.com/notebooks/paperA_genotyping/results/marker_panel_26May30/).

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES

Table S1. Per-split per-genotype sample counts.

Stratified 80/10/10 partition with deterministic seed 20241022. Pre-deduplication target distribution 700 (C) : 500 (B) : 350 (A) : 300 (D) : 100 (E) : 50 (F). Near-duplicates removed by weighted 11-mer Jaccard ≥ 0.95 within each genotype. Dataset FASTA SHA-256 da2e9aff...f25c8e0c; splits CSV SHA-256 149b0780...df9432395. Post-dedup = Train + Validation + Test for every genotype.

Table S2. Full pairwise discriminatory counts for all 15 genotype pairs.

Strict rule: some base has a frequency $\geq 95\%$ in one genotype and $\leq 5\%$ in the other. Mode rule: the modal base differs between the two genotypes. Computed on the MAFFT-aligned 1,828-sequence cohort (NC_003977.2, 3,182 bp). The B–C strict count (11) is approximately 60-fold lower than the 667 positions obtained from a single-pair pre-alignment comparison; the comparable modal-base count (238) is approximately 2.8-fold lower (see Discussion).

Table S3. Complete list of 238 B–C mode-discriminatory positions.

Reference-coordinate (NC_003977.2) positions at which genotypes B and C differ in modal base. Eleven of these also meet the strict criterion (modal-base frequency $\geq 95\%$ in one genotype and $\leq 5\%$ in the other) and are annotated with the B and C modal bases and their frequencies. Gene-region assignment uses approximate aligned gene boundaries.

Table S4. Per-test-accession Jaccard similarity to the training + validation pool.

For each of the 189 held-out test accessions, the maximum weighted 11-mer Jaccard similarity to any training or validation sequence, computed within and across genotype. Maximum within-genotype

similarity 0.948 (0/189 reaching the 0.95 deduplication threshold); maximum cross-genotype similarity 0.621 (0/189 reaching 0.80), confirming effective leakage control.

Table S5. Paired test-set predictions for the McNemar test.

Per-accession CNN and Transformer predictions on the 189 held-out test sequences. Both correct, 164; CNN correct only, 24; Transformer correct only, 0; both wrong, 1. McNemar's exact two-sided $p = 1.19 \times 10^{-7}$; the exact test was used because one discordant cell was zero, which makes the asymptotic chi-square approximation inappropriate.

Table S6. Minimal genotype-discriminatory marker sets and held-out six-way classification accuracy (test n = 189).

Held-out six-way accuracy of an L2-regularised logistic-regression classifier (positions selected on the train + validation pool, evaluated on the test split) for each marker set: all 664 population mode-discriminatory positions (100%); the single ~300 bp preS1/polymerase amplicon, NC_003977.2 ~2,881–3,180 (100%); an interpretable decision tree using ≤ 22 positions (99.47%); genotype-private single alleles, 67 positions (99.47%); and the minimal modal set-cover, 5 positions (92.06%). Leakage-controlled five-fold stratified cross-validation with feature selection inside folds: $99.62\% \pm 0.28\%$. Genotype-private fixed alleles ($\geq 95\%$ in one genotype, $\leq 5\%$ in all others) existed for genotypes A, B, D, and F (1, 3, 2, and 62 positions, respectively) but not for C or E. Reproducible analysis and data: [notebooks/paperA_genotyping/07_marker_panel_genotyping_colab.ipynb](#) and [results/marker_panel_26May30/](#).

Table S7. Genotype-consensus pairwise genetic distances.

Jukes–Cantor-corrected nucleotide distances (%) between the six genotype-level consensus sequences (modal base per alignment column) derived from the deduplicated 1,828-sequence

whole-genome alignment. The matrix is symmetric with a zero diagonal. Genotype F is the most divergent (mean 13.9% to the other genotypes) and genotype A the least (9.4%), while genotypes D and E form the closest pair (6.6%); these distances underlie the neighbour-joining trees in Figure S6 and were not used for model training, classification, or marker selection.